

**REPRESENTATION OF MOTHERHOOD IN AFRICAN AMERICAN
LITERATURE: A SOCIO-CULTURAL AND GENDER ANALYSIS**

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Abstract

This study seeks to assess the portrayal of black mothers in African American literature, spanning from slave narratives to postmodern works, with a focus on race and gender dimensions. It examines the interpretation and depiction of motherhood in various historical phases, analyzing texts such as Frances Ellen Watkins Harper's "The Slave Mother" (1854) to Alice Walker's "The Color Purple" (1982). These selected works delve into social, cultural, race, and gender aspects, contributing to an exploration of the nuanced construction of motherhood.

Key words

Motherhood; Gender Discrimination; Race; Gender Issues; Cultural Norms; Relationship

Introduction

The historical depiction of black motherhood has had an impact on the way black women are viewed as mothers in American society. Through the analysis of

African American literature, it becomes evident that motherhood is a social construct that changes with societal values. The deep connection between black motherhood and family life reflects evolving ideas about motherhood from being domesticated to liberated, as seen in different periods of literary and historical development. This study aims to show how black motherhood has transformed from being a marginalized and silent figure to becoming a vocal source of empowerment and resistance against racism and sexism for black women.

Motherhood relates to the unique relationship between a mother and a child that resonates reciprocal feelings of love and affection. The mother achieves this attachment through ceaseless attention and the child responds to the love showing his/her attachment to the mother. It helps a baby to learn to be sociable. Motherhood is an experience shaped by social context and culture. Societal norms define motherhood as a sacred and powerful spiritual path for women and a key aspect of their lives. Every society holds its own unique mythology surrounding motherhood and the notion of motherhood has been transforming throughout the course of history. Motherhood, as a persistent theme in literary works, has been viewed in different lights and presented in diverse ways. Andrea O'Reilly, in her book *From Motherhood to Mothering*, argues that motherhood is not simply a biological function, but rather a cultural practice that is constantly shaped by societal and economic influences. She contends that the meaning of motherhood is not fixed and universal, but instead varies depending on the specific time and place. O'Reilly maintains that the concept of motherhood is contingent on social and cultural norms and varies based on the values and expectations of each culture.

Materials and Methods

In order to carry out this research, a qualitative research was utilized design, following a systematic method to gather information from sources. According to John W. Creswell in *Research Design*, qualitative research is focused on exploring

and comprehending the meanings that individuals or groups attach to social or human issues. This method is relevant for this study as it provides with a deeper understanding of cultural, historical, identity, race, and gender-related issues. The study accounts for collecting, analyzing, as well as, interpreting data, primarily using written documents and texts as data collection tools. To gain a thorough understanding of socio-cultural, race, and gender issues, primary data has been collected from the writings of African American authors from the era of Slavery to the Postmodern phase, and secondary data includes references from textbooks, internet sources, articles, papers, author biographies, journals, and other relevant works.

Results

This research investigates the perspectives of motherhood discussed by Adrienne Rich in *Of Woman Born: Motherhood as Experience and Institution*, Andrea O'Reilly in *Mother Outlaws: Theories and Practices of Empowered Mothering*, and Sara Ruddick in *Maternal Thinking: Toward a Politics of Peace*, all of whom emphasize the central importance of maternal work in a woman's life. Additionally, the study examines Cornel West's views on racism in *Race Matters* (1993) to explore cultural and racial issues, as he argues that "nihilism" - a sense of worthlessness - is the primary barrier to positive race relations in the United States. Additionally, Rich presents two main perspectives on motherhood: that of motherhood as personal experience and motherhood as an institutionalized role. She explains these dual interpretations by stating that motherhood encompasses a woman's reproductive capacity and her relationship with children, as well as the societal institution that seeks to ensure these aspects, and women themselves, are subjugated by men. This institution has been a fundamental component of various social and political systems. Ruddick's book *Maternal Thinking: Toward a Politics of Peace* (1989) delves into the realm of motherhood. She argues that mothering is

a form of caregiving involving three actions: protecting, nurturing, and training. She explains that mothers perceive children's needs for protection, nurturance, and guidance, and strive to meet these needs with care and respect, rather than neglect or aggression.

Discussion

Barbara Christian, a feminist critic, suggests that Frances Harper's primary focus in her writing is to highlight the struggles faced by African American men and women. Specifically, in her book *Black Women Novelists*, Christian states that orators such as Frederick Douglass, William Wells Brown, and Frances Harper worked to counter the negative depictions of black men and women in the South from the 1830s to the onset of the Civil War. Christian's interpretation underscores Harper's deep concern for the plight of black individuals. As an orator, Harper recounts the experiences of black women in the South, who suffered under a system of racism and sexism. Recognizing the challenges faced by black mothers, Harper seeks to raise awareness of their harsh reality through her literary work, aiming to alleviate the dehumanizing effects of the slave system. "The Slave Mother" provides a realistic portrayal of the US slavery system, focusing on its relevance to the study of motherhood through its exploration of the social and cultural aspects of slavery. The poem emphasizes a particularly cruel aspect of chattel slavery, the separation of children from their mothers for the purpose of slave trade. It humanizes the mother's anguish at the loss of her son, as children were considered the most cherished possession. Linda, the slave mother in *Incidents*, endures similar hardships. Due to societal and cultural pressures, poverty, and other challenges faced by black slaves, both mothers undergo immense trials while fulfilling their responsibilities.

Jacobs' autobiographical work *Incidents in the Life of a Slave Girl* (1861) provides a detailed account of the challenges faced by a slave in a society plagued by racism. Under the pseudonym Linda Brent, Jacobs chronicles her life from

being born into slavery in 1813 to gaining her freedom in 1851. The narrative specifically emphasizes Linda's quest for freedom and her battles with the social and gender inequalities inherent in slavery.

Sandra Gilbirt and Susan Gubar, in their work "The Madwoman in the Attic," argue that women writers have historically encountered demeaning expectations when seeking a public voice in literature. Unless they hid their work under pseudonyms or chose to remain anonymous, women were often expected to downplay their abilities and focus on subjects deemed suitable for their perceived lesser capacity.

Bland suggests that women who exhibit true womanhood qualities face difficulties when trying to assert themselves in the public sphere. When women uphold true womanhood, it is challenging for them to speak out against oppression. Jacobs, however, defies the norms of true womanhood. She confronts the challenges of fighting against injustice as both a slave and a woman/mother. In order to successfully write her narrative and share her understanding of slavery, Jacobs speaks out and establishes her identity first as a slave, then as a fugitive woman/mother, and ultimately as an author.

Dunbar's poem "Lonesome" also portrays the challenges and pain of African American mothers as they strive for their children's well-being. This poem is derived from his collection of poetry *Lyrics of a Lowly Life* (1896), and illustrates the construction of motherhood in American society and the struggles made for freedom. Dunbar conveys his profound affection for his mother through the poem, and explicitly addresses racial and gender issues in his poetry. The speaker reflects on his sorrow at his mother's departure for a trip, feeling a sense of loneliness and likening the empty house to a nest without a bird, exhibiting the deep bond between the speaker and his mother.

Howells explains that Dunbar's poetry in dialect effectively conveys important concepts and tells the stories of marginalized individuals, which have

often been poorly represented in music. Dunbar's poetry adheres to conventional structures and topics, and he celebrates his African heritage with pride. Howells' viewpoint is insightful as it shows the advancement and cultural pride of African-Americans.

Dunbar's use of dialect in his poetry was condemned by critics who believed it portrayed a negative image of black lives. Donald A. Petesch, in his work "A Spy in the Enemy's Country: The Emergence of Modern Black Literature," references Jean Wagner's perspective on Dunbar's poetry, stating that it is a "second-hand instrument irreparably tainted by the degrading themes imposed upon it by the enemies of black people". Petesch supports Wagner's argument by revealing that many critics view Dunbar's dialect poetry as reflecting a bleak and humiliating portrayal of black people. This perspective is important as it sheds light on the harsh realities of black life depicted in Dunbar's dialect poetry.

Similarly, *The Autobiography of an Ex-Colored Man* (1913) highlights Johnson's candid and realistic portrayal of black society, race relations, and the struggles faced by black individuals. The novel follows the journey of a protagonist of mixed race who finds it difficult to belong to either racial group. The character, who remains unnamed, appears white enough to pass as a white person but deeply identifies with his mother's black heritage. He enjoys a happy childhood with his mother but, after her passing, he moves to different locations. Initially, he aspires to become a renowned black American composer, but he abandons this dream out of fear after witnessing a group of white people setting fire to a black man in rural South.

Likewise, in *A Voice from the South*, Cooper explains the challenges faced by black women, stating that they are "faced with a double burden of being both women and African American, yet are not recognized in either capacity" (134). This highlights the struggles of black women who suffer from both racial and gender-based discrimination and are restricted from marrying white men. Despite

facing hardship, these women prioritize their children's needs. To protect her son's emotional well-being, the mother tells him that his father is white when he questions his racial identity.

Johnson's *The Autobiography* delves into the plight of an unnamed black mother, showcasing her unwavering commitment to her son's future amidst societal barriers. Despite the challenging circumstances as a single black woman, she navigates the intricacies of her community and ensures her son is well-supported, even while facing the burdens of racial and single motherhood in society. Throughout her life, she remains a devoted, loving caretaker to her son, exhibiting resilience and sacrificing her own well-being to fulfill her maternal duties.

In Giovanni's "Mothers," the poet explores her complex feelings for her mother. The poem, found in her collection *My House* (1972), delves into the societal and cultural expectations placed on mothers. Through the perspective of a young child, the poem not only recounts the story of the poet's mother but also examines her experiences growing up. The repetition of the word "remember" highlights the poet's connection to the past, while the use of words like "dark" and "night" conveys a sense of uncertainty in the child's surroundings. This uncertainty is particularly evident in the third stanza, where the speaker recalls her mother always sitting in the dark, creating a sense of mystery and confusion for the child.

Morrison's *Sula* (1973) mirrors Giovanni's "Mothers" as it delves into the challenges faced by a black mother navigating unforeseen circumstances that lead her from naivety to actively advocating for her children. The story unfolds in a black community in Medallion, Ohio between 1919 and 1965, and revolves around the intertwined lives of childhood friends Nel Wright and Sula Peace. While the two begin as inseparable companions, their individual paths diverge as they mature. Sula, raised by her grandmother Eva, who has only one leg, challenges

societal norms and rejects traditional roles of women, such as marriage and motherhood.

Conclusion

The concept and portrayal of motherhood have evolved significantly throughout history, particularly during the antebellum and post-bellum eras. In those times, the idea of motherhood was based on commitment, selflessness, and confinement to domestic duties. Black women, especially during the period of slavery, were expected to fulfill multiple roles, encompassing those traditionally assigned to black women, black men, and white women, without the rights to marry or have a family life. While some societal and political changes occurred after the Civil War, the responsibilities and roles of black women in African American society remained largely unchanged.

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